

Economic Stochastic Model Predictive Control Using the Unscented Kalman Filter[★]

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Abstract: Economic model predictive control is a popular method to maximize the efficiency of a dynamic system. Often, however, uncertainties are present, which can quickly lead to lower performance and constraint violations. In this paper, a new approach is proposed that incorporates the square root Unscented Kalman filter directly into the optimal control problem to estimate the states and to propagate the mean and covariance of the states to consider noise from disturbances, parametric uncertainties and state estimation errors. The covariance is propagated up to a predefined “robust horizon” to limit open-loop covariances, and chance constraints are introduced to maintain feasibility. Often variables in chemical engineering are non-negative, which however can be violated by the Unscented Kalman filter leading to erroneous predictions. This problem is solved by log-transforming these variables to ensure consistency. The approach was verified and compared to a nominal nonlinear model predictive control algorithm on a semi-batch reactor case study with an economic objective via Monte Carlo simulations.

Keywords: Robust control, Uncertain dynamic systems, Model-based control, Co-ordinate transformations, Nonlinear filters

1. INTRODUCTION

Batch reactors are common in many sectors in the chemical industry including pharmaceuticals, polymers, food products, biotechnology and electronic chemicals due to their flexibility to handle different products and product grades. The control of batch processes is challenging, since these are operated at unsteady state, often exhibit large time constants and are frequently highly nonlinear. This motivates the use of nonlinear model predictive control (NMPC). NMPC applications have been mostly based on scheduling multiple models, successive linearization or empirical nonlinear models, while NMPC implementations using first principle models are becoming increasingly feasible due to the advent of automatic differentiation and more efficient optimization algorithms (Nagy and Braatz, 2003).

NMPC was developed to deal with nonlinear dynamic processes with constraints and strongly coupled, multivariable plants. At each sampling time NMPC solves an open-loop optimal control problem (OCP) based on an explicit model of the dynamic system with initial conditions set to the current state estimate to determine a finite sequence of control actions to take (Maciejowski, 2002). Feedback enters this procedure implicitly through the state and bias update from the measurements at each sampling time (Mesbah, 2016). The objective of the NMPC is usually to track a set point, but the true objective is to maximize profit. Therefore, in economic MPC (EMPC) the cost function is directly given by the quantity to be maximized (Lucia et al., 2014), which has attracted significant attention

in recent years (Rawlings and Amrit, 2009). For batch reactors the objective is usually some property of the final product and hence the control problem leads to a shrinking horizon implementation (Nagy and Braatz, 2003).

The performance of the NMPC algorithm strongly depends on the accuracy of the dynamic model used. Models of real processes often involve substantial uncertainties, including parametric uncertainties, unaccounted disturbances and state estimation errors. In particular, economic MPC often drives the system to its constraints, which makes the systematic consideration of uncertainties essential to prevent constraint violations (Lucia et al., 2014).

Most work to consider uncertainties explicitly has been in robust NMPC (RN MPC), which assumes that uncertainties are deterministic and bounded. Important methods for RN MPC are min-max NMPC (Chen et al., 1997), tube-based NMPC (Mayne et al., 2011) and multi-stage NMPC (Lucia, 2014). An alternative to RN MPC is given by stochastic NMPC (SN MPC), which assumes that the uncertainties present are given by known probability distributions. In SN MPC constraints are probabilistic and given by either chance or expectation constraints. The regulation of the probability of constraint violations allows the adjustment of the conservativeness of the solution.

In Cannon et al. (2009) a simple procedure for SN MPC is introduced based on successive linearization of the nonlinear system and subsequent application of a probabilistic tube method. A popular tool in SN MPC is given by the so-called polynomial chaos expansion (PCE), which is an efficient alternative to Monte Carlo simulations to propagate probabilistic uncertainties. A major disadvantage of this approach is that the complexity with respect to the number of uncertainty parame-

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ters scales exponentially and handling state estimation error is non-trivial (Fagiano and Khammash, 2012). Maciejowski et al. (2007) proposed a method based on the Markov chain Monte Carlo approach, which is generally more efficient than common Monte Carlo sampling based techniques, but does not take gradient information into account. Lastly, multi-stage MPC has been used to solve SNMPC problems, which however quickly becomes intractable due to the computational complexity scaling exponentially with the size of the time horizon, number of uncertainty parameters and uncertainty levels (Goodwin et al., 2009).

In Bradford and Imsland (2017) the Unscented Kalman filter (UKF) is used to estimate the state for output feedback model predictive control and propagate the state estimation error and additive noise from disturbances forward in time. The predicted Gaussian distributions of the states were used to impose probabilistic constraints. A similar approach is given in Farrokhsiar and Najjaran (2012) to propagate state estimation error and additive noise for the control of nonholonomic mobile robots. In addition, Liu et al. (2014) and Völz and Graichen (2016) show that the unscented transformation (UT) can be used to efficiently propagate additive disturbance errors. Lastly, in Heine et al. (2006) the UT is used to propagate parametric uncertainties. A general advantage of the UT is the linear scaling with respect to the number of uncertain parameters.

In this paper the previous work is unified to take into account state estimation error from the square root UKF, noise from additive disturbances and lastly parametric uncertainties. In addition, it is shown how log-transformations can be used to introduce lower bounds on estimated variables. This is particularly important in chemical engineering, for which many variables cannot be negative. Lastly, the method uses the square root UKF rather than the standard UKF, since it has beneficial numerical stability and guaranteed positive semi-definiteness of the state covariances, which is vital for the repeated application of the UKF in the propagation steps of the algorithm. Further, the square root UKF is approximately 20% computationally cheaper than the standard UKF (Van Der Merwe and Wan, 2001). The approach was tested on the same semi-batch reactor differential algebraic equation (DAE) system as in Bradford and Imsland (2017) with parametric uncertainties added. On this DAE system a challenging economic MPC problem with shrinking horizon was formulated. The robustness of the approach was verified with 4 uncertain parameters and compared to a nominal NMPC approach via Monte Carlo simulations.

The paper is divided into the following sections. In the next Section the general SNMPC problem is formulated. In the third Section the square root UKF is introduced and utilised to solve the SNMPC problem. Further, the concepts "robust horizon", log-transformation and linear joint state constraints are outlined. The case study to test the procedure is formulated in Section 4. Section 5 gives the results of the Monte Carlo simulations for the case study. In the last Section conclusions were drawn from the simulation results.

2. NONLINEAR MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL WITH LINEAR CHANCE CONSTRAINTS

The dynamic system we consider is given by a general discrete time stochastic nonlinear system with parametric uncertainties and additive noise. The states and the parameters enter the nonlinear equation system in a non-additive fashion, such that

it is practical to write them jointly as x_a . The dynamic system can be described by:

$$x(k+1) = f(x_a(k), u(k)) + w(k) \quad (1)$$

$$y(k) = h(x_a(k), u(k)) + \nu(k) \quad (2)$$

where k is the discrete time stage, $x_a = [x^T, \theta^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x \times n_\theta = L}$ denotes the augmented state vector with states and uncertain parameters with a joint dimension of L , $x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ denotes the system states, $u \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ represents the control inputs, $y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ denotes the system measurements and $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}$ denotes the parametric uncertainties of the model; the additive disturbance term w lies in \mathbb{R}^{n_x} and the additive measurement noise ν lies in \mathbb{R}^{n_y} . The equations $f: \mathbb{R}^L \times \mathbb{R}^{n_u} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ and $h: \mathbb{R}^L \times \mathbb{R}^{n_u} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ represent the system dynamics of the states and the measurements respectively.

The parametric uncertainties are assumed to be Gaussian distributed with mean vector $m_\theta(k)$ and covariance matrix $\Sigma_\theta(k)$ at stage k . The additive disturbances $w(k)$ and $\nu(k)$ are assumed to be zero mean independent normal random variables with variances $\Sigma_w(k)$ and $\Sigma_\nu(k)$ at stage k respectively. The probability density of the initial state $x(0)$ is assumed to be normal with mean $\hat{x}(0)$ and covariance $\Sigma_x(0)$.

Assuming that we are at stage n , let \mathcal{Y}_n stand for the measurements collected thus far. Subsequently, $\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{Y}_n}(\cdot)$ and $\mathbb{P}_{\mathcal{Y}_n}(\cdot)$ denote the expectation and probability conditioned on \mathcal{Y}_n respectively (Yan and Bitmead, 2005). The goal of the SNMPC algorithm at stage n is to determine a control sequence over a finite time horizon to adjust the probability distributions of the states to optimize an objective, while adhering to predefined probabilistic constraints, given imperfect information through \mathcal{Y}_n . A general SNMPC problem formulation at stage n can be given as follows, with deterministic constraints on the inputs and joint, linear chance constraints on the states:

Finite-horizon SNMPC problem with chance constraints

$$\underset{\mathbf{u}_N}{\text{minimize}} \quad \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{Y}_n}(J(N, x(n), \mathbf{u}_N))$$

subject to

$$x(n+k+1) = f(x_a(k), u(k)) + w(n+k)$$

$$y(n+k) = h(x_a(k), u(k)) + \nu(n+k) \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbb{P}_{\mathcal{Y}_n}(l_k^{iT} x(n+k) \leq g_k^i) \geq 1 - p_k^i \\ \forall (k, i) \in \{1, \dots, N\} \times \{1, \dots, n_g\}$$

$$u(n+k) \in \mathbb{U}_k \quad \forall k \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$$

where the length of the time horizon is given by N , n_g denotes the number of linear state constraints, $l_k^i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ and $g_k^i \in \mathbb{R}$ define each linear state constraint, the decision variable constraints are represented by $\mathbb{U}_k \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$, $\mathbf{u}_N := \{u(n), \dots, u(n+N-1)\}$ is a collection of inputs over the finite horizon N from an initial stage n and $J(N, x(n), \mathbf{u}_N)$ is the probabilistic objective function. The joint chance constraints on the states are set to be violated by a frequency of $p_k^i \in (0, 1) \subset \mathbb{R}$ probability.

3. INCORPORATION OF THE SQUARE ROOT UNSCENTED KALMAN FILTER

3.1 Transformation of variables with lower bound

First principle equations for batch processes are commonly given as continuous differential equations, which can be discretized using numerical integration techniques to obtain equations in the form of Eq. (1). In this work orthogonal collocation

was used for numerical integration, for more information please refer to Chachuat (2007). The log-transformation is, however, directly applied to the continuous differential equation system.

Many variables in chemical engineering are non-negative due to physical constraints, such as temperatures, concentrations, volumes, etc.. The methods available in literature to incorporate state constraints in the UKF are not suitable for our specific problem, since these are discontinuous and cannot be managed by the gradient-based NLP solver (Simon, 2010). Instead, we suggest to log-transform the variables to ensure a lower bound on the variables. Let x' be the variable that cannot be lower than a . Then define x to be equal to:

$$x = \log(x' - a) \quad (4)$$

If we now work with x in the problem rather than x' , then x' is guaranteed to remain larger than a , i.e. we have implicitly introduced the following constraint:

$$x' > a \quad (5)$$

The differential equation of x' can then be transformed in the following way to obtain the required differential equation of x :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{dx'}{dt} \frac{1}{x' - a} \quad (6)$$

The transformation does not allow the value 0 for x' , if a is set to 0, however it is usually enough to take a sufficiently small value of x as approximation, i.e. an initial value of x' equal to 0 may be replaced by setting x to a large negative number.

Lastly, given that we know x is normally distributed with mean \hat{x} and covariance Σ_x , i.e. $x \sim \mathcal{N}(\hat{x}, \Sigma_x)$, x' then follows a log-normal distribution, with mean and covariance given by (Halliwell, 2015):

$$\hat{x}'_i = \exp\left(\hat{x}_i + \frac{\Sigma_{x_i,i}}{2}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$\Sigma_{x'_i,j} = \exp\left(\hat{x}_i + \hat{x}_j + \frac{\Sigma_{x_i,i} + \Sigma_{x_j,j}}{2}\right) (\exp(\Sigma_{x_i,j}) - 1) \quad (8)$$

where \hat{x}' and $\Sigma_{x'}$ are the mean and covariance of x' respectively

Eq. (7) can be used to obtain the state estimate for the true variable x' from x with the corresponding covariance matrix from Eq. (8).

3.2 Propagation of state probability distributions using the square root Unscented Kalman filter

The problem in Eq. (3) is intractable, since it requires the determination and propagation of conditional probability densities of the states through nonlinear transformations in the form of Eq. (1) and Eq. (2) (Yan and Bitmead, 2005). Instead we use the UT to approximate the mean and covariance of this probability density, which is the probability density of the states and measurements. In our case the uncertain input is given by the states and uncertain parameters, both of which are assumed to be Gaussian distributed at all stages. The UT creates a set of sampling points according to several rules, which depend on the mean and covariance of the Gaussian distributed input. The predicted mean and covariance of the UT are accurately estimated up to third order (Simon, 2006), which is a major advantage of the UT over more conventional first order linearization approaches.

To obtain the state estimate the Kalman filter equations are used at stage n . For the propagation of the mean and covariance of the states the UT is repeatedly applied to Eq. (1), assuming at each stage that the output follows a Gaussian distribution. This approach is summarised in the Algorithm 1 box and illustrated in Fig. 1. The equation system is given such that $\hat{x}(n|n)$, the state estimate, is also calculated given the current measurement $y(n)$, the previous state estimate $\hat{x}(n-1|n-1)$, the previous state covariance $\Sigma_x(n-1|n-1)$ and the previous control input $u(n-1)$. Guidelines on how to set the scaling parameters ($\omega_i^\mu, \omega_i^c, \lambda$) and definitions of $\text{qr}(\cdot)$, \cdot/\cdot and $\text{cholupdate}(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)$ required for the square root UKF can be found in Van Der Merwe and Wan (2001).

The considered OCP in Eq. (3) is open-loop, which does not account for the NMPC to have reduced covariances through feedback by the state and bias update. This leads to the predicted conditional covariances to increase with k and therefore the OCP becoming increasingly conservative with larger time horizons. Eventually the OCP becomes infeasible (Yan and Bitmead, 2005). The ‘‘robust horizon’’ is utilised as in Bradford and Inslan (2017), up to which the covariances are propagated to address the problem of growing covariances with the length of the time horizon. Hence, for the square root UKF in the Algorithm 1 box, equations were added, such that the covariance matrix is constant after a pre-defined ‘‘robust horizon’’ t_R . This is similar to Yan and Bitmead (2005) who propagates the covariance at the first stage from a Kalman filter in linear MPC, but with the added flexibility to propagate the covariance up to the ‘‘robust horizon’’ since for output feedback the amount of information gained at each stage is different for each problem. Farrokhsiar and Najjaran (2012) introduces so-called ‘‘fake measurements’’ to limit the covariances. This is an interesting approach to take into account information gained to learn parameters, but is on the other hand expensive since it requires additional equations in the MPC formulation.

Fig. 1. Illustration of UKF SNMPC algorithm: Each Sigma point resembles a different input, which are then propagated through the nonlinear transformation to the next stage as indicated by the red lines. These are then used to estimate the mean and covariance of the Gaussian distribution of the states at the next stage. The probability of violating the chance constraint shown is given by the area under the pdf.

Algorithm 1: Square root Unscented Kalman filter with additive noise and parametric uncertainty

Initialization

Input: $\hat{x}(n-1|s)$, $\Sigma_x(n-1|s)$,
 $u(n-1)$, $y(n)$, λ , ω^μ , ω^c , t_R , n , N
 $m_\theta(n+k)$, $\forall k \in \{1, \dots, N\}$,
 $\Sigma_\theta(n+k)$, $\forall k \in \{1, \dots, N\}$
 $\Sigma_w(n+k)$, $\Sigma_v(n+k)$ $\forall k \in \{1, \dots, N\}$
 $f(\cdot)$, $h(\cdot)$

For $s = n-1, k = 0$ and $s = n, k \in \{1, \dots, N\}$

Definition of Sigma points

$$\hat{x}_a(n+k-1|s) = [\hat{x}(n+k-1|s)^T m_\theta(n+k-1)^T]^T \quad (9a)$$

$$\Sigma_a^{1/2}(n+k-1|s) = \text{diag}(\Sigma_x^{1/2}(n+k-1|s), \Sigma_\theta^{1/2}(n+k-1)) \quad (9b)$$

$$\mathcal{X}(n+k-1|s) = [\hat{x}_a(n+k-1|s) \quad \hat{x}_a(n+k-1|s) + \sqrt{L+\lambda} \Sigma_a^{1/2}(n+k-1|s) \quad \hat{x}_a(n+k-1|s) - \sqrt{L+\lambda} \Sigma_a^{1/2}(n+k-1|s)] \quad (9c)$$

Covariance and mean approximation of predictions

$$\mathcal{X}_i(n+k|s) = f(\mathcal{X}_i(n+k-1|s), u(n+k-1)) \quad (10a)$$

$$\hat{x}(n+k|s) = \sum_{i=0}^{2L} \omega_i^\mu \mathcal{X}_i(n+k|s) \quad (10b)$$

$$\forall k \leq t_R \quad \Sigma_x^{1/2}(n+k|s) = \text{qr}([\sqrt{\omega_1^c}(\mathcal{X}_{1:2L}(n+k|s) - \hat{x}(n+k|s)) \quad \Sigma_w^{1/2}(n+k)]) \quad (10c)$$

$$\forall k \leq t_R \quad \Sigma_x^{1/2}(n+k|s) = \text{cholupdate}(\Sigma_x^{1/2}(n+k|s), \mathcal{X}_0(n+k|s) - \hat{x}(n+k|s), \omega_0^c) \quad (10d)$$

$$\forall k > t_R \quad \Sigma_x^{1/2}(n+k|n) = \Sigma_x^{1/2}(n+k-1|n) \quad (10e)$$

Covariance and mean approximation of observations

$$\phi_i(n|n-1) = h(\mathcal{X}_i(n|n-1), u(n-1)) \quad (11a)$$

$$\hat{y}(n|n-1) = \sum_{i=0}^{2L} \omega_i^\mu \phi_i(n|n-1) \quad (11b)$$

$$\Sigma_{yy}^{1/2}(n|n-1) = \text{qr}([\sqrt{\omega_1^c}(\phi_{1:2L}(n|n-1) - \hat{y}(n|n-1)) \quad \Sigma_v^{1/2}]) \quad (11c)$$

$$\Sigma_{yy}^{1/2}(n|n-1) = \text{cholupdate}(\Sigma_{yy}^{1/2}(n|n-1), \phi_0(n|n-1) - \hat{y}(n|n-1), \omega_0^c) \quad (11d)$$

$$\Sigma_{xy}(n|n-1) = \sum_{i=0}^{2L} \omega_i^c (\mathcal{X}^{(i)}(n|n-1) - \hat{x}(n|n-1))(\phi^{(i)}(n|n-1) - \hat{y}(n|n-1))^T \quad (11e)$$

Update of states from available measurements

$$K(n) = (\Sigma_{xy}(n|n-1) / \Sigma_{yy}^{1/2 T}(n|n-1)) / \Sigma_{yy}^{1/2}(n|n-1) \quad (12a)$$

$$\hat{x}(n|n) = \hat{x}(n|n-1) + K(n)(y(n) - \hat{y}(n|n-1)) \quad (12b)$$

$$U = K(n) \Sigma_{yy}^{1/2}(n|n-1) \quad (12c)$$

$$\Sigma_x(n|n) = \text{cholupdate}(\Sigma_x(n-1|n-1), U, -1) \quad (12d)$$

3.3 Probability constraints

The probability constraints on the states of interest are in the form of linear constraints as defined in Eq. (3):

$$\mathbb{P}(l^T x \leq g) \geq 1 - \epsilon \quad (13)$$

Using Chebychev's inequality the probability constraints in (13) can be robustly transformed to the following equation (Liu et al., 2014):

$$l^T \hat{x} + \sqrt{\beta l^T \Sigma_x l} \leq g \quad (14)$$

where \hat{x} and Σ_x are the mean and covariance of x respectively and $\beta = \frac{1-\epsilon}{\epsilon}$

For the untransformed variables Eq. (13) can be directly used with the mean and covariance predicted by the square root UKF. For the transformed variables we instead use the mean and covariance given by Eq. (7) and Eq. (8) respectively, since we want to place the probability constraints on the true states. This is also done so that we can define the robust horizon on this covariance, by adding the following equation:

$$\forall k > t_R \quad \Sigma_{x'}(n+k|n) = \Sigma_{x'}(n+k-1|n) \quad (15)$$

3.4 Square root UKF SNMPC formulation

Given linear chance constraints of the form in Eq. (13), a simplified SNMPC formulation can be stated as follows:

Finite horizon SNMPC problem with incorporated square root UKF and chance constraints

$$\underset{\mathbf{u}_N}{\text{minimize}} \quad \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{Y}_n}(J(N, x(n), \mathbf{u}_N))$$

subject to

$$\mathbb{P}_{\mathcal{Y}_n}(l_k^T x(n+k) \leq g_k^i) \geq 1 - p_k^i$$

$$\forall (k, i) \in \{1, \dots, N\} \times \{1, \dots, n_g\}$$

$$u(n+k) \in \mathbb{U}_k \quad \forall k \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$$

(9) – (12) square root UKF based on transformed variable x
 (7), (8), (15) Variance and mean of untransformed variable x' (16)

where the probability constraints can be reformulated as shown in Section 3.3. The equations of the square root UKF given in Algorithm 1 are implemented in Eq. (16) as equality constraints to obtain the Gaussian distributions of the state estimate and of all predicted states up to the final time horizon. If the variables were transformed and we wish to place the probability constraint on the "true" variables, Eq. (7), Eq. (8) and Eq. (15) need to be used in addition to obtain the mean and covariance required for the reformulated probability constraint and robust horizon. The open-loop problem can then be used in a receding horizon fashion to obtain a SNMPC algorithm as shown in the box for Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2: Square root UKF SNMPC with receding horizon

Initialize: Supply $\hat{x}(0|0)$, $\Sigma_x(0|0)$, $u(0)$ and define (16)
 At each sampling time $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

- Take measurements $y(n)$
- Solve (16) with $\hat{x}(n-1|n-1)$, $\Sigma_x(n-1|n-1)$, $u(n-1)$, $y(n)$ and obtain $u(n)$, $\hat{x}(n|n)$, $\Sigma_x(n|n)$
- Apply $u(n)$ to the real system

4. SEMI-BATCH REACTOR CASE STUDY

4.1 Semi-batch reactor model

To test the procedure the same case study as in Bradford and Imsland (2017) based on a DAE system in Fogler (1999) is used, however parametric uncertainties were added and all the states were log-transformed. The following series reaction takes place in the reactor with H_2SO_4 as catalyst:

The reactions are first order. The first reaction step is exothermic, while the second reaction step is endothermic. A heat exchanger is utilised to control the temperature. The following DAE system describes the dynamic behaviour of the semi-batch reactor:

$$\dot{C}'_A = (-k_{1A}C'_A + (\theta_1 - C'_A)\frac{F}{V'})/C'_A, \quad (17a)$$

$$\dot{C}'_B = (0.5k_{1A}C'_A - k_{2B}C'_B - C'_B\frac{F}{V'})/C'_B, \quad (17b)$$

$$\dot{C}'_C = (3k_{2B}C'_B - C'_C\frac{F}{V'})/C'_C, \quad (17c)$$

$$\dot{T} = \left(\frac{(\theta_2(T_a - T') - F\theta_1 C_{PA}(T' - T_0))}{(C'_A C_{PA} + C'_B C_{PB} + C'_C C_{PC})V' + \theta_4 C_{PH_2SO_4}} + \frac{(-\Delta H_{Rx1A}k_{1A}C'_A - \Delta H_{Rx2B}k_{2B}C'_B)V'}{(C'_A C_{PA} + C'_B C_{PB} + C'_C C_{PC})V' + \theta_4 C_{PH_2SO_4}} \right) / T', \quad (17d)$$

$$\dot{V} = F/V', \quad (17e)$$

$$k_{1A} = \theta_3 \exp\left(-E_{1A}\left(\frac{1}{420} - \frac{1}{T'}\right)\right), \quad (17f)$$

$$k_{2B} = A_2 \exp\left(-E_{2B}\left(\frac{1}{400} - \frac{1}{T'}\right)\right), \quad (17g)$$

$$C'_A = \exp(C_A), \quad C'_B = \exp(C_B), \quad C'_C = \exp(C_C) \quad (17h)$$

$$T' = \exp(T), \quad V' = \exp(V) \quad (17i)$$

where C'_A , C'_B , C'_C are the concentrations in mol dm^{-3} of species A , B and C respectively, T' is the temperature in K of the reactor and V' is the liquid volume in dm^3 . C_A , C_B , C_C , T and V are the log-transformed states of C'_A , C'_B , C'_C , T' and V' respectively. The deterministic parameters were kept at their nominal values, which can be found in Fogler (1999). The uncertain parameters are jointly given by the vector θ , which are assumed to be normally distributed, with constant mean $m_\theta = [4, 45000, 0.08, 100]^T$ and constant covariance $\Sigma_\theta = \text{diag}([0.1, 2e7, 1.6e-4, 5])$. The control inputs of the problem are given by the flow rate of pure A entering the reactor F in dm^3h^{-1} and the temperature of the heat exchanger T_a in K.

In compact form we can write $x' = [C'_A, C'_B, C'_C, T', V']^T$, $x = [C_A, C_B, C_C, T, V]^T$ and $u = [F, T_a]^T$. Using orthogonal collocation the continuous time equations can be given as a discrete time equation system in the form:

$$x(k+1) = f(x(k), u(k)) + w(k) \quad (18)$$

where $f(x(k), u(k))$ describes the DAE system in Eq. (17) and $w(k)$ is additive Gaussian noise with a constant covariance matrix $\Sigma_w = \text{diag}([1e-3, 1e-3, 1e-3, 1e-6, 1e-6])$.

Lastly, the measurement dynamics need to be defined, which are given by the following equation:

$$y(k) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} x'(k) + \nu(k) \quad (19)$$

where $\nu(k)$ is additive Gaussian noise with a constant covariance matrix $\Sigma_\nu = \text{diag}([1e-3, 1e-3, 1e-3])$.

4.2 SNMPC problem

The OCP to be solved is formulated below. The economic objective is to maximize the amount of C at a fixed final batch time with a penalty for excessive control actions. The feed rate can be varied between $0\text{dm}^3\text{h}^{-1}$ and $250\text{dm}^3\text{h}^{-1}$ and the heat exchanger temperature can be adjusted between 270K and 500K . The liquid volume inside the semi-batch reactor is constrained to lie below 800dm^3 , while the temperature is constrained to lie below 440K . The OCP problem is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{u_N}{\text{minimize}} && -(\hat{x}_2(n+N|n) + \hat{x}_4(n+N|n)) + \Delta U^T S \Delta U \\ & \text{subject to} && \\ & && \hat{x}'_3(n+k|n) + \sqrt{\beta \Sigma_{x'_{3,3}}(n+k|n)} \leq 440 \quad \forall k \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & && \hat{x}'_4(n+k|n) + \sqrt{\beta \Sigma_{x'_{4,4}}(n+k|n)} \leq 800 \quad \forall k \in \{1, \dots, N\} \\ & && u(n+k) \in [0, 250] \times [270, 500] \quad \forall k \in \{0, \dots, N-1\} \\ & && (9) - (12) \text{ square root UKF based on transformed variable } x \\ & && (7) - (8), (15) \text{ variance and mean of true variable } x' \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $\beta = \frac{\epsilon}{1-\epsilon}$, $\Delta U = [u(n+k) - u(n+k-1)]_{k \in \{1, \dots, N-1\}}$ and $S = \text{diag}([8e-6, 2e-6])$. For Eqs. (9) - (12), (15) the robust horizon t_R was set to 2, the required scaling parameters can be determined from Van Der Merwe and Wan (2001) with $\alpha = 0.9$, $\beta = 2$ and $\kappa = 1$, $f(\cdot)$ is defined in Eq. (17) and Eq. (18) and $h(\cdot)$ in Eq. (19).

The problem objective is given at a fixed final time, such that a shrinking horizon algorithm was used, defined in the Algorithm 3 box.

Algorithm 3: Square root UKF SNMPC with shrinking horizon

Initialize: Supply $\hat{x}(0|0)$, $\Sigma_x(0|0)$, $u(0)$ and define (16) with $N := N_t$, where N_t is the final time horizon to be reached
 At each sampling time $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

- Take measurements $y(n)$
- Solve (16) with $\hat{x}(n-1|n-1)$, $\Sigma_x(n-1|n-1)$, $u(n-1)$, $y(n)$ and obtain $u(n)$, $\hat{x}(n|n)$, $\Sigma_x(n|n)$
- Apply $u(n)$ to the real system
- Redefine (16) with $N := N - 1$
- Terminate when $N = 0$

5. SIMULATION STUDIES

The final batch time was set to $4h$ with the total number of sampling points set to $N_t = 20$. The OCP in Eq. (20) was solved repeatedly using Casadi (Andersson, 2013) by employing direct collocation in Python. The degree of the polynomials was set to 4 and placed according to the Radau quadrature rule. A single polynomial is used for each control interval. The nonlinear programming problem was solved by employing Ipopt (Wächter and Biegler, 2006). IDAS (Hindmarsh et al., 2005) was utilised to simulate the "real" nonlinear equation system for the various Monte Carlo samples. At

time $n = 1$, Algorithm 3 needs to be initialized by supplying it with the "previous" covariance matrix, mean and control action. These were set to $\hat{x}(0|0) = [\log(1e-3), \log(1e-3), \log(1e-3), \log(290), \log(100)]^T$, $\Sigma_x(0|0) = \text{diag}([1e-3, 1e-3, 1e-3, 1e-3, 1e-3])$ and $u(0) = [0, 290]^T$ respectively.

The case study was first simulated for the case of the uncertain parameters fixed at their mean values for the "real" system to show the corresponding trajectory and control inputs with $\epsilon = 0.05$. In Fig. 5 the trajectories of the states are shown in red with the corresponding state estimates at each discrete time as green crosses. We can see that the state estimates are generally accurate, however there is some deviation for concentration C towards the end. Both the reactor temperature and volume leave some distance to their respective constraints to account for the uncertainties in the problem.

To test the robustness of the method 200 Monte Carlo simulations were performed, i.e. by sampling different realizations of parameters, additive disturbances and initial conditions for the real system, again with $\epsilon = 0.05$. The various trajectories can be seen in Fig. 3. For comparison purposes a nominal NMPC was run on 200 Monte Carlo simulations, for which the results are shown in Fig. 2. Here it can be seen why the algorithm previously left distance to the constraints due to the uncertainty from parameters and disturbances, since otherwise the constraints would be easily violated. The UKF SNMPC overall performs well and leads to a relatively small number of constraint violations, while the nominal NMPC can be seen to violate both constraints substantially.

Lastly, the method was run for 3 different values of ϵ and for the nominal NMPC algorithm, with 100 Monte Carlo samples. The obtained objective values are illustrated in Fig. 4 as a box plot to highlight the trade-off between conservativeness and performance. The red line in the box plot indicates the median of the objective values, while the blue lines represent the upper and lower quartiles. The black lines give the smallest and largest value attained from the simulations, excluding outliers, shown as red crosses. We can clearly see that the median amount of C at the final batch time consistently increases with ϵ as expected, since an increase in ϵ leads to less conservativeness. The nominal NMPC algorithm leads to the largest amount of C on average due to the consistent constraint violations, as can be seen in Fig. 2.

6. CONCLUSION

Overall a new algorithm is proposed for SNMPC with efficient formulation of the probability constraints, which has been shown to be an efficient means to account for uncertainties from state estimates, disturbances and parameters for an economic model predictive control problem of a semi-batch reactor. The algorithm was able to keep nearly all 200 Monte Carlo simulations within the constraints, while it was shown that a nominal NMPC algorithm leads to significant constraint violations. In addition, important issues such as the prevention of negative concentrations were addressed by log-transformations.

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Fig. 2. 200 Monte Carlo trajectories of the "real" system from a nominal NMPC algorithm

Fig. 3. 200 Monte Carlo trajectories of the "real" system from the SNMPC algorithm based on the OCP in Eq. (20) with $\epsilon = 0.05$

Fig. 4. Box plot of 100 Monte Carlo simulations for different values of ϵ for the UKF SNMPC algorithm based on the OCP in Eq. (20) and for the nominal NMPC algorithm

Fig. 5. Monte Carlo simulation trajectories of the "real" system from the SNMPC algorithm based on the OCP in Eq. (20) with $\epsilon = 0.05$

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